

Early Medieval Confucianism

By Keith Knapp, The Citadel

Entry tags: Confucian (rujia 儒家) Traditions, Early Medieval Confucian Traditions, Early Medieval Confucianism, Religious Group, Imperial Confucian Traditions, Chinese Religion, Confucianism, Yellow and Yangzi Rivers Region

Early Medieval Confucians (Ru 儒) were individuals who were well-versed in the Five Classics (Wujing 五经) and their commentaries, as well as the Analects (Lunyu 论语) and the Classic of Filial Piety (Xiaojing 孝经). They viewed the founders of their tradition as the Duke of Zhou (Zhougong 周公) and Confucius (Kongzi 孔子), which is why contemporaries sometimes called Confucianism "The Teachings of the Duke of Zhou and Confucius" (Zhou Kong zhi dao 周孔之道). Members of this group referred to their tradition using several other names as well, such as the Teachings of the Confucians (Rujiao 儒教), the Teachings of Confucius (Kongjiao 孔教), the Teachings of the Sage (Shengjiao 圣教), and Teachings of the Way (Daojiao 道教). Many early medieval Confucians believed in the existence of spirits and all agreed on the importance of sacrifices. However, offerings had to be made to gods (nature deities and ancestors) sanctioned in the Five Classics and worship could not be excessive. The most important religious rite was the emperor's sacrifice to Tian 天 (Heaven) in the capital's southern suburb. Of course, there were some Confucians, such as Fan Zhen 范镇 (ca.450-510), who denied the existence of spirits. Others, such as Huangfu Mi 皇甫谧 (215-282), thought that the deities of Heaven and Earth were vigorously surveilling human activities and manifesting auspicious and inauspicious omens to reward good and punish bad moral conduct. Early Medieval Confucians put a particular stress on perfecting themselves by behaving according to the Three Ritual Codes (Sanli 三礼): Book of Rites (Li ji 礼记), the Rites of Zhou (Zhouli 周礼), and the Book of Etiquette and Ceremonies (Yili 仪礼). Self-cultivation was inter-connected with social behavior: a Confucian cultivated herself/himself by fulfilling social roles and performing good deeds. Early medieval courts especially valued Confucians for their ritual knowledge and command of the Five Classics. As a result, they often served emperors as advisors on ritual matters, Erudites (boshi 博士) at the Imperial College, and as tutors to the imperial princes. For early medieval Confucians, the main purpose of government was to secure the welfare of commoners and enhance their moral fiber through the process of moral transformation (jiaohua 教化). This meant setting an example for others through one's personal conduct and establishing schools that taught the Five Classics and proper deportment. One did not have to hold public office to have a positive effect on others through moral transformation. Early Medieval Confucians frequently served in office, yet some, to maintain their moral integrity, chose to become recluses, such as Huangfu Mi. Oftentimes, they would then establish a private school at their residence. The loose social organization that underpinned medieval Confucianism was precisely the master-student networks created through schools. Early Medieval Confucians were by no means exclusivist. Several of them also embraced either Daoism or Buddhism. Although the inner chapters of Ge Hong's 葛洪 (283-343) *The Master who Embraces Simplicity* (Baopuzi 抱朴子) are devoted to ways of seeking immortality, his outer chapters express a Confucian critique on social and political matters. Yan Zhitui 颜之推 (531-591) viewed Confucianism as the outer teachings, while Buddhism were the more important inner teachings. Nevertheless, other Confucians, such as He Chengtian 何承天 (370-447) and Fan Zhen were vehement critics of Buddhism, while Sun Sheng 孙盛 (ca. 301-373) was well known for his criticism of Daoism.

Date Range: 220 CE - 589 CE

Region: Northern Wei and the Liu-Song

Region tags: China, East Asia, Yangzi River Valley, Yellow River Valley

The Northern Wei (北魏) was founded in 386 by the

Tuoba 拓跋 (Tabgac) branch of the Xianbei 鲜卑 (Sarbi) people who originated in the northeast corner of present-day Inner Mongolia. It was the longest lasting of the Northern Dynasties (386-581). Its first capital was in Shengle 盛乐 near present-day Hohhot 胡特好特. In 399, Emperor Daowu 道武 moved the capital to Pingcheng (present-day Datong). In 494, Emperor Xiaowen 孝文 moved the capital to Luoyang 洛阳 in the Yellow River Valley. The Yellow River Valley is a large alluvial plain with rich soil, but limited rainfall and prone to flooding. During the Northern Wei, the main agricultural crop was millet. Other crops were wheat, barley, and soybeans. Due to steppe influence, there was much stockbreeding as well. Millet, yogurt, and mutton were commonly eaten. In 420, Liu Yu 刘裕, a northern emigre strongman, founded the Song Dynasty, which is known to history as the Liu-Song 刘宋 (420-479) to distinguish it from the much more famous Song 宋 Dynasty (960-1279). It was the second of the Southern Dynasties, each of which had its capital in Jiankang 建康 (modern-day Nanjing 南京). Coursing through the Yangzi River Valley was the Yangzi River, which was much slower and broader than the Yellow River. The terrain of the Yangzi River Valley was much more rugged and hilly than the Yellow River Valley and had considerably more rainfall. The staple crop was rice. Southerners were characterized as liking to consume rice, fish, and tea.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Keith N. Knapp. "Confucian Learning and Influence". (Albert Dien E., Keith Knapp Nathaniel, Ed.), *The Cambridge History of China, Volume II: The Six Dynasties (220-589)*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2019.
- Source 2: Suzhen Chen. "The position and evolution of Ruist learning". (Xingpei Yuan , Wenming Yan , Chuanxi Zhang , Yulie Lou), *The History of Chinese Civilization: Qin, Han, Wei, Jin, and the Northern and Southern dynasties (221 B.C.E. – 581 C.E.)*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2012.
- Source 3: Keith N. Knapp, "Early Imperial Confucianism." (Jennifer Oldstone-Moore, Ed.) *Oxford Handbook of Confucianism*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, forthcoming.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <https://ctext.org>

– Source 1 Description: The Chinese Text Project provides the complete Chinese text a number of primary sources relevant to medieval Confucianism, such as the Kongzi jiaoyu 孔子家语, Yanshi jiaxun 严氏家训, Baopuzi 抱朴子, and the Gaoshi zhuan 高士传.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

General Variables

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: The Confucian scriptures of early medieval China were the Five Classics (Wujing 五经): the Book of History (Shujing 书经 or Shangshu 尚书), Book of Poetry (Shijing 诗经), Book of Changes (Yijing 易经 or Zhouyi 周易), Book of Rites (Liji 礼记), and the Chunqiu Annals (Chunqiu 春秋), the Three Ritual Texts (Sanli 三礼: the Book of Rites, the Book of Ceremony and Etiquette [Yili 仪礼], and the Zhou Rites [Zhouli 周礼]), the Chunqiu's Three Commentaries (Chunqiu sanzhuàn 春秋三传), the Analects (Lunyu 论语), and the Classic of Filial Piety (Xiaojing 孝经).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Are they written:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Are they oral:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Revealed by a high god:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Inspired by high god:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– Yes

Notes: This is a qualified "yes." Confucius supposedly edited four of the Five Classics and authored the fifth classic, the Spring and Autumn Annals to discourage disloyalty and unfiliality. For some early medieval Confucians, Confucius was merely a man. For others, particularly those influenced by the Confucian apocrypha (Chenwei 讖纬) texts, Confucius was the Uncrowned King who had a supernatural birth, and thus was a semi-divine human being.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– Yes

Notes: With perhaps the exception of the Spring and Autumn Annals, all of the other Confucian scriptures were believed to be written by human beings. Nevertheless, the authors were not ordinary people, but the sages of antiquity, men whose actions and words manifested the dao 道, the heavenly order of things.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

Notes: By the early medieval period, the scriptures were fixed. By late second century, the Five Classics were literally set in stone.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– No

Notes: During the Han (202 BCE-220 CE), twice there were conferences called by the emperor to supervise the interpretation of the Five Classics. However, I don't know of similar efforts during the early medieval period.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: Since early medieval China was a manuscript culture only a select group of men could be trained in transmitting the scriptures. One had to be accepted as a student by a master Ru. After one proved his worth as a student, he could then make a copy the texts in which the master specialized. If the student wanted to learn another scripture, he would have to study with another master Ru.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– No

Notes: The Five Classics (The Book of Changes, Book of Poetry, Book of History, Book of Rites, Spring and Autumn Annals) had been fixed by the first century BCE. However, in the second century CE, there were efforts to expand the canon; hence, the number of Classics was expanded to seven. What were the seven texts was not fixed. The Seven Classics (Qijing 七经) inscribed on stone in 175 CE were the Book of Changes, Book of History, Book of Poetry, the Chunqiu Annals, the Gongyang zhuan (公羊传), and the Great Master Dai's Book of Rites (Da Dai Liji 大戴礼记). The fifth-century History of the Later Han (Hou Han shu 后汉书) relates that the seven are the Book of Changes, Book of Poetry, Book of History, Book of Rites, the Zhou Rites (Zhouli), the Book of Etiquette and Ceremony (Yili), and the Analects (Lunyu).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

— Yes

Notes: Competition was made manifest in Confucian essays written against Buddhism and Daoism, as well as court debates between representatives of the Three Religions.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

— Yes

Notes: Many early medieval Confucians were open to embracing either Buddhism or Daoism as well. Often they justified it by saying the two teachings were the same or complemented each other. One way to do this was to recognize Confucianism as the outer (secular) teaching and either Daoism or Buddhism as the inner (spiritual) teaching.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

— Yes

Notes: Conflicts only rarely happened. This occurred at the national level in the form of empire-wide suppressions of either Buddhism or Daoism. The court would force monks and nuns to return to secular life, while confiscating monasteries and their riches.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– I don't know

Notes: The remains of the mingtang 明堂 "The Hall of Light or the Bright Hall" of the Northern Wei capital of Pingcheng offers us some sense of what the size of this religious building was. Each of its four sides were 42 meters long and its diagonal was 60 meters. The moat that surrounded it was 289 to 294 meters in diameter.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is extremely difficult to answer this question. Nearly all Confucians at this point were educated people. Nevertheless, we do not even know what percentage of the early medieval population was literate.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Notes: Early medieval Confucians were not formally organized. You became a Ru (Confucian) through receiving an education in the Five Classics and their commentaries, the Analects, and the Classic of Filial Piety. Hence, any person who received such an education could be considered a Ru.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

Notes: Emperors were given large tombs. However, in an effort to curb lavish burials (and perhaps curb tomb robbery), Wei (220-265) and Western Jin (265-317) emperors prohibited establishing offering shrines, stone stelae, or stone animals near tombs. Nevertheless, Southern Dynasties (317-589) emperors began to once again erect a row of large stone statues in front of their tombs.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Temples:

— Yes

Notes: There were a few temples dedicated to Confucius, but they were not numerous. There was a temple devoted to Confucius at his birthplace in Qufu 曲阜, and a shrine dedicated to him at the Imperial University (Taixue 太学) in the capital. Other government schools probably also had shrines dedicated to Confucius and his disciples. There were, however, numerous ancestral temples. The largest of these was the imperial ancestral temple (Taimiao 太庙), where the emperor worshiped seven generations of his ancestors. There were also ancestral temples to past emperors of the ruling dynasty. The History of Wei (Wei shu 魏书) provides a description of the ancestral temple dedicated to Gao Huan 高欢 (496-547). See Steinhardt, *Chinese Architecture in an Age of Turmoil*, p.191. It seems that high-ranking officials also had ancestral temples. Most well-to-do people worshipped their ancestors in the main hall of their family compound.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Altars:

— Yes

Notes: As part of the state cult, the Capital usually had a large number of altars. There were two altars to the gods of the soil: the Taishe 太社 (Grand Altar to the Soil) and the Dishe 帝社 (Imperial Altar to the Soil), as well as one to the god of grains: the Taiji 太稷. If a court followed the classical interpretations of Zheng Xuan 郑玄 (127-200), then there would be a Round Mound (Yuanqiu 圆丘) altar in the southern suburb, where a sacrifice would be conducted at the Winter Solstice to Heaven, as well as the Southern Suburban Altar, where in the first month, the emperor performed the most important ritual dedicated to Heaven on High (Tiandi 天帝 or Shangdi 上帝). In the northern suburb, a Square Mound (fangqiu 方丘) Altar and the Northern Suburban Altar were established. This is where sacrifices were made to the highest earth deities. Courts subscribing to the theories of Wang Su 王肃 (195-256), would have neither the Round Mound nor the Square Mound altars; instead, there was just the Southern Suburban Altar and the Northern Suburban Altar. Courts that subscribed to Zheng Xuan's theories would also have altars to the Five Thearchs (Wudi 五帝) who represented the Five Phases (wuxing 五行). No matter whether a court followed the theories of Zheng Xuan or Wang Su, there were also altars to the Sun, Moon, the Five Planets, Lord Wind (Fengbo 风伯), Commander Cloud (Yunshuai 云帅), Commander Thunder (Leishuai 雷帅), Commander Rain (Yushuai 雨帅), the Four Rivers, the Four Seas, the First Farmer (Xiannong 先农), and the sage emperors.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Devotional markers:

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: The Hall of Light (Mingtang 明堂), the Circular Moat (Biyong 辟雍), the Observatory or Spirit Terrace (Lingtai 灵台)

Notes: All three of these structures were only erected in the capital for the emperor's use. The Mingtang was built in the shape of the cosmos. It was the ritual structure in which the emperor would perform important rites throughout the year. The Circular Moat was a ritual structure, which served as a school for nobles. As the name implies, it was surrounded by a moat. The Lingtai was a tower from the top of which the Heavens could be observed.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is extremely difficult to answer this question. Nearly all Confucians at this point were educated people. Nevertheless, we do not even know what percentage of the population during the early medieval period were literate. Perhaps roughly no more than 5% of the population.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Notes: This is a tricky question to answer because early medieval Confucians were not a formally constituted group. They were men who shared the same education and thus had similar opinions and beliefs. Nevertheless, although they probably didn't believe they were proselytizing and recruiting new members, the purpose of Confucian moral transformation was to get people to act and think morally, according to the Confucian dictates, which ultimately made them Confucian in outlook.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– No

Notes: Confucianism did not have religious professionals.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– No

Notes: Nevertheless, it was assumed that a good Confucian would not only cultivate his own goodness, but also work to morally transform others through helping them become better humans.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– No

Notes: Confucianism did not have any religious professionals.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– No

Notes: Nevertheless, it was assumed that a good Confucian would not only cultivate his own goodness, but also work to morally transform others through helping them become better humans.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: I believe that Confucianism became the imperial ideology in the late first century BCE. In the early medieval era, Confucian ideas strongly influenced court rhetoric, policy, education, and law. Most emperors demonstrated their loyalty to Confucianism by worshipping Confucius and lecturing on the *Xiaojing* (Classic of Filiality).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– No

Notes: No because Confucianism had no priests

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

— Yes

Notes: The state cults dedicated to the gods sanctioned by the Confucian Classics were paid for by the government, as were shrines dedicated to Confucius in state sponsored schools. Ancestral temples and shrines of private families were not paid for by the government.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

— Yes

Notes: Yes, the emperor was the chief officiant of Confucianism. As the Son of Heaven, he was the one who was supposed to undertake the sacrifices given to the highest god. His officials, on his behalf, carried out sacrifices to lesser officially sanctioned divinities.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

— Yes

Notes: Nearly each official had religious duties in addition to his secular duties. He had to participate in the state cult to the deities sanctioned in the classics. If there was a natural catastrophe, such as a drought or flood, a local official had to engage in religious activities to end the problem.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

— Yes

Notes: This is clearest in view of the complicated and prolonged Confucian mourning rites. During the medieval period, if an official performed the mourning rites incorrectly or in a non-conventional manner, other bureaucrats might impeach him, which might ultimately lead to his dismissal from office. If an official's father reached the age of 80 and had no other sons to look after him, the court would dismiss the official from office, so that he could administer to his father.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– No

Notes: Although the legal code was not coterminous with the Confucian rites, some aspects of it overlapped with Confucian norms. For example the Wei Dynasty (220-265) made it illegal for fathers and sons to have separate finances. This is a way of saying that they had to live together, which was a Confucian dictate.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– Yes

Notes: During the early medieval period, the state frequently rewarded men who exemplified filial piety. This often took the form of gifts, exemptions from taxes, and even public office. For examples of this, see my article "Exemplary Everymen."

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Is iconography present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– At home

– Some public spaces

Notes: There is some evidence that images of Confucius and his disciples were painted on the walls of some schools and government offices. Images of filial children and outstanding women appear on sarcophagi, pictorial bricks, funerary beds, and lacquered goods in the tombs of private individuals. It could well be that some lacquered goods with these images interred with the deceased could have been also used in their lifetime.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: There were images of auspicious beasts that appear when a ruler embodies virtue.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– Yes

Notes: Images of stories of filial children and outstanding women were probably meant for a couple of purposes. One might have been to remind descendants to behave well and fulfill their family obligations. Another might have been to tell others that the deceased had similar virtues to the exemplars depicted in her/his tomb. Yet another was probably to indicate to others that the family of the deceased was one that uphold Confucian virtues.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Humans:

– Yes

Notes: Confucian iconography of the period almost entirely consists of images of human exemplars of Confucian virtues. They are usual images of filial sons, outstanding women, and worthy ministers.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Other features of iconography:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Notes: Since Confucians were not a formal group, there was no conception of apostasy.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (seen as being part of a related larger religious group)

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: There were a number of sacred spaces for Confucian scholars. The most important of these was a temple to Confucius at Qufu, his birthplace and site of his tomb. There was also a shrine dedicated to Confucius at the Imperial University, where either the emperor or the crown prince would frequently offer sacrifices to Confucius. By the sixth century probably most government schools had shrines to Confucius and his disciples. The imperial ancestral temple in the capital, along with other ancestral temples and shrines established by literati would have also been considered sacred. The "Bright Hall" mingtang 明堂 was another sacred structure that was periodically built in the capitals of the early medieval period. The altars of the Northern and Southern Suburban sacrifices were sites dedicated to sacred practice.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Notes: Yes, as part of the Confucian state cult, sacrifices were offered to the deities of important geographical features, such as rivers and mountains.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– No

Notes: Since the Confucians were not an organized group, it did not have recognized leaders. Nevertheless, there were men who were deemed outstanding Confucians because of their extensive knowledge of the classics and their exemplary moral conduct. These men were known as tongru 通儒 "Confucian Scholars who have Comprehensive Knowledge." No doubt, they were treated as informal Confucian leaders.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: Competition was made manifest in Confucian essays written against Buddhism and Daoism, as well as court debates between representatives of the Three Religions.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: Many early medieval Confucians were open to embracing either Buddhism or Daoism as well. Often they justified it by saying the two teachings were the same or complemented each other. One way to do this was to recognize Confucianism as the outer (secular) teaching and either Daoism or Buddhism as the inner (spiritual) teaching.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: Conflicts only rarely happened. This occurred at the national level in the form of empire-wide suppressions of either Buddhism or Daoism. The court would force monks and nuns to return to secular life, while confiscating monasteries and their riches.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Notes: Early medieval Confucians were not formally organized. You became a Ru (Confucian) through receiving an education in the Five Classics and their commentaries, the Analects, and the Classic of Filial Piety. Hence, any person who received such an education could be considered a Ru.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Notes: This is a tricky question to answer because early medieval Confucians were not a formally constituted group. They were men who shared the same education and thus had similar opinions and beliefs. Nevertheless, although they probably didn't believe they were proselytizing and recruiting new

members, the purpose of Confucian moral transformation was to get people to act and think morally, according to the Confucian dictates, which ultimately made them Confucian in outlook.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– No

Notes: Confucianism did not have religious professionals.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– No

Notes: Nevertheless, it was assumed that a good Confucian would not only cultivate his own goodness, but also work to morally transform others through helping them become better humans.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– No

Notes: Confucianism did not have any religious professionals.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– No

Notes: Nevertheless, it was assumed that a good Confucian would not only cultivate his own goodness, but also work to morally transform others through helping them become better humans.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: I believe that Confucianism became the imperial ideology in the late first century BCE. In the early medieval era, Confucian ideas strongly influenced court rhetoric, policy, education, and law. Most emperors demonstrated their loyalty to Confucianism by worshipping Confucius and lecturing on the *Xiaoqing* (Classic of Filiality).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– No

Notes: No because Confucianism had no priests

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– Yes

Notes: The state cults dedicated to the gods sanctioned by the Confucian Classics were paid for by the government, as were shrines dedicated to Confucius in state sponsored schools. Ancestral temples and shrines of private families were not paid for by the government.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, the emperor was the chief officiant of Confucianism. As the Son of Heaven, he was the one who was supposed to undertake the sacrifices given to the highest god. His officials, on his behalf, carried out sacrifices to lesser officially sanctioned divinities.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– Yes

Notes: Nearly each official had religious duties in addition to his secular duties. He had to participate in the state cult to the deities sanctioned in the classics. If there was a natural catastrophe, such as a drought or flood, a local official had to engage in religious activities to end the problem.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– Yes

Notes: This is clearest in view of the complicated and prolonged Confucian mourning rites. During the medieval period, if an official performed the mourning rites incorrectly or in a non-conventional manner, other bureaucrats might impeach him, which might ultimately might lead to his dismissal from office. If an official's father reached the age of 80 and had no other sons to look after him, the court would dismiss the official from office, so that he could administer to his father.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– No

Notes: Although the legal code was not coterminous with the Confucian rites, some aspects of it overlapped with Confucian norms. For example the Wei Dynasty (220-265) made it illegal for fathers and sons to have separate finances. This is a way of saying that they had to live together, which was a Confucian dictate.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– Yes

Notes: During the early medieval period, the state frequently rewarded men who exemplified filial piety. This often took the form of gifts, exemptions from taxes, and even public office. For examples of this, see my article "Exemplary Everymen."

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Notes: Since Confucians were not a formal group, there was no conception of apostasy.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is extremely difficult to answer this question. Nearly all Confucians at this point were educated people. Nevertheless, we do not even know what percentage of the early medieval population was

literate.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is extremely difficult to answer this question. Nearly all Confucians at this point were educated people. Nevertheless, we do not even know what percentage of the population during the early medieval period were literate. Perhaps roughly no more than 5% of the population.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (seen as being part of a related larger religious group)

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– No

Notes: Since the Confucians were not an organized group, it did not have recognized leaders. Nevertheless, there were men who were deemed outstanding Confucians because of their extensive knowledge of the classics and their exemplary moral conduct. These men were known as tongru 通儒 "Confucian Scholars who have Comprehensive Knowledge." No doubt, they were treated as informal Confucian leaders.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: The Confucian scriptures of early medieval China were the Five Classics (Wujing 五经): the Book of History (Shujing 书经 or Shangshu 尚书), Book of Poetry (Shijing 诗经), Book of Changes (Yijing 易经 or Zhouyi 周易), Book of Rites (Liji 礼记), and the Chunqiu Annals (Chunqiu 春秋), the Three Ritual Texts (Sanli 三礼: the Book of Rites, the Book of Ceremony and Etiquette [Yili 仪礼], and the Zhou Rites [Zhouli 周礼]), the Chunqiu's Three Commentaries (Chunqiu sanzhuo 春秋三传), the Analects (Lunyu 论语), and the Classic of Filial Piety (Xiaojing 孝经).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Are they oral:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Inspired by high god:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– Yes

Notes: This is a qualified "yes." Confucius supposedly edited four of the Five Classics and authored the fifth classic, the Spring and Autumn Annals to discourage disloyalty and unfiliality. For some early medieval Confucians, Confucius was merely a man. For others, particularly those influenced by the Confucian apocrypha (Chenwei 讖纬) texts, Confucius was the Uncrowned King who had a supernatural birth, and thus was a semi-divine human being.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– Yes

Notes: With perhaps the exception of the Spring and Autumn Annals, all of the other Confucian scriptures were believed to be written by human beings. Nevertheless, the authors were not ordinary people, but the sages of antiquity, men whose actions and words manifested the dao 道, the heavenly order of things.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

Notes: By the early medieval period, the scriptures were fixed. By late second century, the Five Classics were literally set in stone.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– No

Notes: During the Han (202 BCE-220 CE), twice there were conferences called by the emperor to supervise the interpretation of the Five Classics. However, I don't know of similar efforts during the early medieval period.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: Since early medieval China was a manuscript culture only a select group of men could be trained in transmitting the scriptures. One had to be accepted as a student by a master Ru. After one proved his worth as a student, he could then make a copy the texts in which the master specialized. If the student wanted to learn another scripture, he would have to study with another master Ru.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– No

Notes: The Five Classics (The Book of Changes, Book of Poetry, Book of History, Book of Rites, Spring and Autumn Annals) had been fixed by the first century BCE. However, in the second century CE, there were efforts to expand the canon; hence, the number of Classics was expanded to seven. What were the seven texts was not fixed. The Seven Classics (Qijing 七经) inscribed on stone in 175 CE were the Book of Changes, Book of History, Book of Poetry, the Chunqiu Annals, the Gongyang zhuan (公羊传), and the Great Master Dai's Book of Rites (Da Dai Liji 大戴礼记). The fifth-century History of the Later Han (Hou Han shu 后汉书) relates that the seven are the Book of Changes, Book of Poetry, Book of History, Book of Rites, the Zhou Rites (Zhouli), the Book of Etiquette and Ceremony (Yili), and the Analects (Lunyu).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– I don't know

Notes: The remains of the mingtang 明堂 "The Hall of Light or the Bright Hall" of the Northern Wei capital of Pingcheng offers us some sense of what the size of this religious building was. Each of its four sides were 42 meters long and its diagonal was 60 meters. The moat that surrounded it was 289 to 294 meters in diameter.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

Notes: Emperors were given large tombs. However, in an effort to curb lavish burials (and perhaps curb tomb robbery), Wei (220-265) and Western Jin (265-317) emperors prohibited establishing offering shrines, stone stelae, or stone animals near tombs. Nevertheless, Southern Dynasties (317-589) emperors began to once again erect a row of large stone statues in front of their tombs.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Temples:

– Yes

Notes: There were a few temples dedicated to Confucius, but they were not numerous. There was a temple devoted to Confucius at his birthplace in Qufu 曲阜, and a shrine dedicated to him at the Imperial University (Taixue 太学) in the capital. Other government schools probably also had shrines dedicated to Confucius and his disciples. There were, however, numerous ancestral temples. The largest of these was the imperial ancestral temple (Taimiao 太庙), where the emperor worshiped seven generations of his ancestors. There were also ancestral temples to past emperors of the ruling dynasty. The History of Wei (Wei shu 魏书) provides a description of the ancestral temple dedicated to Gao Huan 高欢 (496-547). See Steinhardt, *Chinese Architecture in an Age of Turmoil*, p.191. It seems that high-ranking officials also had ancestral temples. Most well-to-do people worshipped their ancestors in the main hall of their family compound.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Altars:

– Yes

Notes: As part of the state cult, the Capital usually had a large number of altars. There were two altars to the gods of the soil: the Taishe 太社 (Grand Altar to the Soil) and the Dishe 帝社 (Imperial Altar to the Soil), as well as one to the god of grains: the Taiji 太稷. If a court was followed the classical interpretations of Zheng Xuan 郑玄 (127-200), then there would be a Round Mound (Yuanqiu 圆丘) altar in the southern suburb, where a sacrifice would be conducted at the Winter Solstice to Heaven, as well as the Southern Suburban Altar, where in the first month, the emperor performed the most important ritual dedicated to Heaven on High (Tiandi 天帝 or Shangdi 上帝). In the northern suburb, a Square Mound (fangqiu 方丘) Altar and the Northern Suburban Altar were established. This is where sacrifices were made to the highest earth deities. Courts subscribing to the theories of Wang Su 王肃 (195-256), would have neither the Round Mound nor the Square Mound altars; instead, there was just the Southern Suburban Altar and the Northern Suburban Altar. Courts that subscribed to Zheng Xuan's theories would also have altars to the Five Thearchs (Wudi 五帝) who represented the Five Phases (wuxing 五行). No matter whether a court followed the theories of Zheng Xuan or Wang Su, there were also altars to the Sun, Moon, the Five Planets, Lord Wind (Fengbo 风伯), Commander Cloud (Yunshuai 云帅), Commander Thunder (Leishuai), Commander Rain (Yushuai), the Four Rivers, the Four Seas, the First Farmer (Xiannong 先农), and the sage emperors.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Devotional markers:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: The Hall of Light (Mingtang 明堂), the Circular Moat (Biyong 辟雍), the Observatory or Spirit Terrace (Lingtai 灵台)

Notes: All three of these structures were only erected in the capital for the emperor's use. The Mingtang was built in the shape of the cosmos. It was the ritual structure in which the emperor would perform important rites throughout the year. The Circular Moat was a ritual structure, which served as a school for nobles. As the name implies, it was surrounded by a moat. The Lingtai was a tower from the top of which the Heavens could be observed.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Is iconography present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– At home

– Some public spaces

Notes: There is some evidence that images of Confucius and his disciples were painted on the walls of some schools and government offices. Images of filial children and outstanding women appear on sarcophagi, pictorial bricks, funerary beds, and lacquered goods in the tombs of private individuals. It could well be that some lacquered goods with these images interred with the deceased could have been also used in their lifetime.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: There were images of auspicious beasts that appear when a ruler embodies virtue.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– Yes

Notes: Images of stories of filial children and outstanding women were probably meant for a couple of purposes. One might have been to remind descendants to behave well and fulfill their family obligations. Another might have been to tell others that the deceased had similar virtues to the exemplars depicted in her/his tomb. Yet another was probably to indicate to others that the family of the deceased was one that uphold Confucian virtues.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Humans:

– Yes

Notes: Confucian iconography of the period almost entirely consists of images of human exemplars of Confucian virtues. They are usual images of filial sons, outstanding women, and worthy ministers.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Other features of iconography:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: There were a number of sacred spaces for Confucian scholars. The most important of these was a temple to Confucius at Qufu, his birthplace and site of his tomb. There was also a shrine dedicated to Confucius at the Imperial University, where either the emperor or the crown prince would frequently offer sacrifices to Confucius. By the sixth century probably most government schools had shrines to Confucius and his disciples. The imperial ancestral temple in the capital, along with other ancestral temples and shrines established by literati would have also been considered sacred. The "Bright Hall" mingtang 明堂 was another sacred structure that was periodically built in the capitals of the early medieval period. The altars of the Northern and Southern Suburban sacrifices were sites dedicated to sacred practice.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Notes: Yes, as part of the Confucian state cult, sacrifices were offered to the deities of important geographical features, such as rivers and mountains.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body.

Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: This is a difficult question to answer because different Confucian scholars had different answers. Fan Zhen was famous for arguing that a person's spirit was inseparable from his body, so when someone died his/her spiritual qualities would disappear as well. Other Confucian scholars, such as Huangfu Mi and Yan Zhitui believed that one's souls survived death, which is why Huangfu Mi feared tomb robbery and Yan Zhitui embraced Buddhism.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Notes: This is a hard question to answer because some early medieval Confucians, such as Huangfu Mi 皇甫谧 and Yan Zhitui 颜之推, believed that the hun soul was distinct from the body, whereas Fan Zhen 范镇 and He Chengtian 何承天 did not.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Other spirit-body relationship:

– Yes [specify]: The body and the spirit are closely linked together

Notes: Fan Zhen believed that the spirit and the body were so closely linked that neither could exist without the other, so when the body died, the spirit also disappeared.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Early medieval Confucians believed that the spirits of Heaven and Earth would put forth auspicious omens when rulers exhibited morally exemplary conduct and would produce inauspicious omens when rulers engaged in particularly egregious behavior. Filial piety stories of the period also indicate that heavenly spirits would take notice of exemplary filial conduct and reward them with miracles. Tales in which people were unjustly put to death, show Heaven causing a miracle to indicate their innocence. Local magistrates who ruled with benevolence could also be rewarded with auspicious omens, as well as miraculous protection against locusts, diseases, and bandits. People who were wrongly put to death could appeal to Heaven to gain permission to punish evildoers.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: The supreme god was designated by a number of different names. They were Tian 天 "Sky

or Heaven," Tiandi 天帝 "Heavenly Lord," Shangdi "Lord on High." Thomas Wilson posits that Heaven and the Lord on High might have been conceived as two separate deities. According to Zheng Xuan 郑玄 (127-200), there were six different heavens: Haotian shangdi 昊天上帝 "Lord on High of the Vast Heaven" and the Wudi 五帝 "the Five Deities" who corresponded to the Wuxing 五行 "Five Phases" and the "Five Directions."

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

— Yes

Notes: The supreme high deity known as Tian 天 (Heaven), Tiandi 天帝 (The Heavenly Emperor), or Tianshen 天神 (The Heavenly Spirit) is frequently depicted as having feelings and acts in a human manner. In early medieval Confucian stories, Tian 天 "Heaven," Tiandi 天帝 "The Heavenly Lord," or Shangdi 上帝 "Lord on High" is moved by perfect filial behavior and thus rewards devoted children. In the case of the famous filial son Dong Yong 董永, Heaven pities his plight as an indentured servant and thus sends down Tiannu 天女 (The Heavenly Female) to earn Dong Yong's freedom through her miraculous weaving. In the case of Guo Ju 郭巨 who decides to bury his young son to have enough food to feed his elderly mother, he digs up a cauldron filled with gold that says, "Heaven has given this gold to Guo Ju ; neither officials nor private persons can take it away." Tianshen 天神 "The Heavenly Spirit" is so impressed by Yang Gong's 羊公 devotion to others that he becomes a student who hands Yang seeds that become jade discs and coins.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– Yes

Notes: This is a hard question to answer. In a way, the emperor is related to the high god; after all, his title is Huangdi 皇帝 "August Deity" and Tianzi 天子 "Son of Heaven." This kin relationship is underlined in that, in the annual Suburban Sacrifice, he presents offerings to Heaven in the capacity of a son honoring his father. Since only the emperor has this special relationship with Heaven, only he can offer this sacrifice. Nevertheless, he is not viewed as a direct emanation of the high god.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, the Heavenly Lord or Lord on High only seems to be concerned with what goes on in China

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Notes: This made clear through the notion of yinde 阴德 "hidden merit." Early medieval Confucians believed that families prospered because their ancestors had accumulated "hidden merit," which meant good deeds that they did not publicize. Even though other people might not see these good actions, Heaven took note of them. See my *_Selfless Offspring_*, 39-41.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:
– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ The supreme high god can reward:
– Yes

Notes: For rulers who govern well, the Heavenly Emperor can cause auspicious omens to appear. For people who embody virtues, the Heavenly Emperor can either send someone to reward him or her, or reward him or her directly.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ The supreme high god can punish:
– Yes

Notes: In tales circulated by Confucian scholars, the spirit world is organized into

a bureaucracy; thus, the supreme being does not punish directly. Instead, a complaint is brought to him by a wronged party and he empowers them to redress the wrong. Nevertheless, if a ruler does wrong, then Heaven, the Heavenly Lord, or the Lord on High can punish directly either through sending down disasters or inauspicious omens.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

— Yes

Notes: Yes, Tian (Heaven) or Tiandi (Heavenly Emperor) can have his emotions stirred by the actions of humans. He can feel pity when the virtuous are in distress or when someone is wrongly condemned.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

— Yes

Notes: Yes, each year the high god is offered food at a sacrificial feast in the southern suburb.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ In trance possession:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Only through monarch

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, previously human spirits that were sacrificed to included the Duke of Zhou, Confucius, the sage emperors, the First Farmer (Shennong 神农), and one's ancestors.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Notes: Avenging spirits were said to be able to physically kill the person who wronged them.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Human spirits can reward:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Human spirits can punish:

– Yes

Notes: This is particularly clear in tales of wronged souls. With Heaven's permission, they can take revenge on the person who wronged them.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, but relatively rarely.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Notes: Dreams are the most frequent way that human spirits communicate with the living.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ In trance possession:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Through divination processes:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Only through specialists:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Communicate with living through other means:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: Medieval Confucian scholars offered sacrifices to various astral deities, such as the Sun, Moon, and the Five Planets, as well as the gods of clouds, winds, rain, and thunder. They also sacrificed to deities of nature, such as the gods of soil and grain, and the most important mountains and rivers. These deities, though, often took human form.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: Archaeological evidence indicates that the gods Fuxi and Nugua were often depicted as being half human and half snake.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: If we look at the state religious cult, it is obvious that there was a variety of supernatural beings, in addition to past human supernatural beings, there were astral supernatural being, as well as deities of nature that had to be venerated through sacrificial feasts.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: This is also a difficult question to answer because different Confucian scholars had different answers. Since he believed that the spirit disappeared with the death of the body, Fan Zhen obviously believed there was no afterlife. He Chengtian thought the ideas of heavens and hells were merely props by which Buddhists tried to get their believers to behave well, so it appears he did not believe in an afterlife either. Huangfu Mi and many other Confucian literati who left explicit burial instructions in their death testaments believed that there was a hereafter. Of those who left death testaments many asked for an austere burial (bozang 薄葬), in which one would be dressed simply, have few grave goods, have a thin coffin, and no tumulus to mark the grave. On the one hand, this would prevent grave robbers from disturbing the soul within the tomb. On the other hand, it would show other spirits and others that you valued simplicity rather than wealth.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Done only by high god:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: The spirits of people who die unjustly often administer punishments on the living. In most cases, though, they have to gain Heaven or the Heavenly bureaucracy's permission to do so. Other deities can also punish the living, but their actions can be appealed to Heaven.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Done randomly:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

Notes: Tian (Heaven) or Tiandi (Heavenly Emperor) ultimately causes a reward to be given, but Heaven might delegate a subordinate to bestow the award.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: With Heaven's permission other supernatural beings can hand out rewards.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

Notes: Tian (Heaven) or Tiandi (Heavenly Emperor) bestows rewards to promote social values, such as filial piety, loyalty, or good governance.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Done randomly:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:
– No
Specific to this answer:
Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:
– No
Specific to this answer:
Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: During the Han (202 BCE -220), right after a person's death, it was normal for Confucians to wash the corpse's body and hair, and then place either a piece of jade, a jewel, or grain within the corpse's mouth. The body was then wrapped in multiple layers of clothes. Since frugality was an important Confucian virtue during this period, Confucians wanted "austere burials" *bozang* 薄葬. Consequently, sometimes they told their descendents that their corpse neither needed to be washed nor was anything to be put in their mouths. They were to be buried in a tomb without a vault, in a simple coffin with thin sides, wearing simple seasonal robes.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Cremation:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Mummification:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Interment:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Corpse is interred some other way:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

Notes: Probably most medieval Confucian scholars had burials like most other upper-class Chinese, which means they were interred with a number of grave goods. Of course, those Confucian scholars who requested an "austere burial" merely wanted a few, special grave goods that demonstrated their virtue,

such as a brush and paper, and certain books, like the Classic of Filial Piety (Xiaojing 孝经).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

Notes: During the early medieval period, upper-class Chinese were usually buried with some articles that they had used in their lifetime. The tomb of the warlord and ultimate founder of the Wei state, Cao Cao 曹操, had a number of tablets that stated "This is the X that Lord Cao used in his Life."

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Valuable items:

– Yes

Notes: Despite requests in death testaments not to be buried with anything of value, unlooted and sometimes even looted upper-class tombs have numerous pieces of valuable porcelain and gold and silver ornaments.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

– Yes

Notes: Huangfu Mi in his death testament tells us that his contemporaries often were buried with jade, pearls, and gold jewelry.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

– Yes

Notes: Well-to-do people were buried with porcelain vessels, bronze coins, and iron swords,

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Other valuable/precious items interred:

– Yes [specify]: Well-to-do people were also buried with mingqi "spirit vessels." These were funerary goods that did not have any practical function, such as model clay wells, chicken coops, and pigsties.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Other grave goods:

– Yes

Notes: A number of the grave goods buried with the upper-class dead were "spirit wares" 明器. These were goods made to be entombed and had no practical value. Many were figurines of animals, servants, and warriors. Some were miniature models of wells, stoves, chicken coops, and animal pens.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: Upper-class Chinese of the period were usually buried in family cemeteries.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

Notes: Upper-class Chinese were usually interred in a joint-burial of husband and wife.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: One of the most important features of the medieval Confucians is their advocacy of specific virtues. These are ren 仁 (humaness, compassion, human-heartedness), yi 义 (righteousness, justice, duty), li 礼 (propriety), zhi 智 (wisdom), xin 信 (trustworthiness), xiao 孝 (filial piety), and zhong 忠 (loyalty).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: This is a difficult question to answer because different Confucian scholars had different answers. Fan Zhen was famous for arguing that a person's spirit was inseparable from his body, so when someone died his/her spiritual qualities would disappear as well. Other Confucian scholars, such as Huangfu Mi and Yan Zhitui believed that one's souls survived death, which is why Huangfu Mi feared tomb robbery and Yan Zhitui embraced Buddhism.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Notes: This is a hard question to answer because some early medieval Confucians, such as Huangfu Mi 皇甫谧 and Yan Zhitui 颜之推, believed that the hun soul was distinct from the body, whereas Fan Zhen 范缜 and He Chengtian 何承天 did not.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– Yes [specify]: The body and the spirit are closely linked together

Notes: Fan Zhen believed that the spirit and the body were so closely linked that neither could exist without the other, so when the body died, the spirit also disappeared.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: This is also a difficult question to answer because different Confucian scholars had different answers. Since he believed that the spirit disappeared with the death of the body, Fan Zhen obviously believed there was no afterlife. He Chengtian thought the ideas of heavens and hells were merely props by which Buddhists tried to get their believers to behave well, so it appears he did not believe in an afterlife either. Huangfu Mi and many other Confucian literati who left explicit burial instructions in their death testaments believed that there was a hereafter. Of those who left death testaments many asked for an austere burial (bozang 薄葬), in which one would be dressed simply, have few grave goods, have a thin coffin, and no tumulus to mark the grave. On the one hand, this would prevent grave robbers from disturbing the soul within the tomb. On the other hand, it would show other spirits and others that you valued simplicity rather than wealth.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: During the Han (202 BCE -220), right after a person's death, it was normal for Confucians to wash the corpse's body and hair, and then place either a piece of jade, a jewel, or grain within the corpse's mouth. The body was then wrapped in multiple layers of clothes. Since frugality was an important Confucian virtue during this period, Confucians wanted "austere burials" *bozang* 薄葬. Consequently, sometimes they told their descendents that their corpse neither needed to be washed nor was anything to be put in their mouths. They were to be buried in a tomb without a vault, in a simple coffin with thin sides, wearing simple seasonal robes.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Cremation:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Mummification:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Interment:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Corpse is interred some other way:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

Notes: Probably most medieval Confucian scholars had burials like most other upper-class Chinese, which means they were interred with a number of grave goods. Of course, those Confucian scholars who requested an "austere burial" merely wanted a few, special grave goods that demonstrated their virtue, such as a brush and paper, and certain books, like the Classic of Filial Piety (Xiaojing 孝经).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Personal effects:

– Yes

Notes: During the early medieval period, upper-class Chinese were usually buried with some articles that they had used in their lifetime. The tomb of the warlord and ultimate founder of the Wei state, Cao Cao 曹操, had a number of tablets that stated "This is the X that Lord Cao used in his Life."

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Valuable items:

– Yes

Notes: Despite requests in death testaments not to be buried with anything of value, unlooted and sometimes even looted upper-class tombs have numerous pieces of valuable porcelain and gold and silver ornaments.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

– Yes

Notes: Huangfu Mi in his death testament tells us that his contemporaries often were buried with jade, pearls, and gold jewelry.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

– Yes

Notes: Well-to-do people were buried with porcelain vessels, bronze coins, and iron swords,

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Other valuable/precious items interred:

– Yes [specify]: Well-to-do people were also buried with mingqi "spirit vessels." These were funerary goods that did not have any practical function, such as model clay wells, chicken coops, and pigsties.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Other grave goods:

– Yes

Notes: A number of the grave goods buried with the upper-class dead were "spirit wares" 明器. These were goods made to be entombed and had no practical value. Many were figurines of animals, servants, and warriors. Some were miniature models of wells, stoves, chicken coops, and animal pens.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: Upper-class Chinese of the period were usually buried in family cemeteries.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

Notes: Upper-class Chinese were usually interred in a joint-burial of husband and wife.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: The supreme god was designated by a number of different names. They were Tian 天 "Sky or Heaven," Tiandi 天帝 "Heavenly Lord," Shangdi "Lord on High." Thomas Wilson posits that Heaven and the Lord on High might have been conceived as two separate deities. According to Zheng Xuan 郑玄 (127-200), there were six different heavens: Haotian shangdi 昊天上帝 "Lord on High of the Vast Heaven" and the Wudi 五帝 "the Five Deities" who corresponded to the Wuxing 五行 "Five Phases" and the "Five Directions."

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: The supreme high deity known as Tian 天 (Heaven), Tiandi 天帝 (The Heavenly Emperor), or Tianshen 天神 (The Heavenly Spirit) is frequently depicted as having feelings and acts in a human manner. In early medieval Confucian stories, Tian 天 "Heaven," Tiandi 天帝 "The Heavenly Lord," or Shangdi 上帝 "Lord on High" is moved by perfect filial behavior and thus rewards devoted children. In the case of the famous filial son Dong Yong 董永, Heaven pities his plight as an indentured servant and thus sends down Tiannu 天女 (The Heavenly Female) to earn Dong Yong's freedom through her miraculous weaving. In the case of Guo Ju 郭巨 who decides to bury his young son to have enough food to feed his elderly mother, he digs up a cauldron filled with gold that says, "Heaven has given this gold to Guo Ju ; neither officials nor private persons can take it away." Tianshen 天神 "The Heavenly Spirit" is so impressed by Yang Gong's 羊公 devotion to others that he becomes a student who hands Yang seeds that become jade discs and coins.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– Yes

Notes: This is a hard question to answer. In a way, the emperor is related to the high god; after all, his title is Huangdi 皇帝 "August Deity" and Tianzi 天子 "Son of Heaven." This kin relationship is underlined in that, in the annual Suburban Sacrifice, he presents offerings to Heaven in the capacity of a son honoring his father. Since only the emperor has this special relationship with Heaven, only he can offer this sacrifice. Nevertheless, he is not viewed as a direct emanation of the high god.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, the Heavenly Lord or Lord on High only seems to be concerned with what goes on in China

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

— Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

— Yes

Notes: This made clear through the notion of yinde 阴德 "hidden merit." Early medieval Confucians believed that families prospered because their ancestors had accumulated "hidden merit," which meant good deeds that they did not publicize. Even though other people might not see these good actions, Heaven took note of them. See my *_Selfless Offspring_*, 39-41.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

— I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

Notes: For rulers who govern well, the Heavenly Emperor can cause auspicious omens to appear. For people who embody virtues, the Heavenly Emperor can either send someone to reward him or her, or reward him or her directly.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

Notes: In tales circulated by Confucian scholars, the spirit world is organized into a bureaucracy; thus, the supreme being does not punish directly. Instead, a complaint is brought to him by a wronged party and he empowers them to redress the wrong. Nevertheless, if a ruler does wrong, then Heaven, the Heavenly Lord, or the Lord on High can punish directly either through sending down disasters or inauspicious omens.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, Tian (Heaven) or Tiandi (Heavenly Emperor) can have his emotions stirred by the actions of humans. He can feel pity when the virtuous are in distress or when someone is wrongly condemned.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, each year the high god is offered food at a sacrificial feast in the southern suburb.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ In trance possession:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Only through monarch

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– No

Specific to this answer:

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, previously human spirits that were sacrificed to included the Duke of Zhou, Confucius, the sage emperors, the First Farmer (Shennong 神农), and one's ancestors.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Notes: Avenging spirits were said to be able to physically kill the person who wronged them.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Human spirits can reward:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Human spirits can punish:

– Yes

Notes: This is particularly clear in tales of wronged souls. With Heaven's permission, they can take revenge on the person who wronged them.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, but relatively rarely.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Notes: Dreams are the most frequent way that human spirits communicate with the living.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ In trance possession:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Through divination processes:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Only through specialists:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Communicate with living through other means:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: Medieval Confucian scholars offered sacrifices to various astral deities, such as the Sun, Moon, and the Five Planets, as well as the gods of clouds, winds, rain, and thunder. They also sacrificed to deities of nature, such as the gods of soil and grain, and the most important mountains and rivers. These deities, though, often took human form.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular

domain of human affairs:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know your basic character (personal essence):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: Archaeological evidence indicates that the gods Fuxi and Nügua were often depicted as being half human and half snake.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: If we look at the state religious cult, it is obvious that there was a variety of supernatural beings, in addition to past human supernatural beings, there were astral supernatural being, as well as deities of nature that had to be venerated through sacrificial feasts.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Early medieval Confucians believed that the spirits of Heaven and Earth would put forth auspicious omens when rulers exhibited morally exemplary conduct and would produce inauspicious omens when rulers engaged in particularly egregious behavior. Filial piety stories of the period also indicate that heavenly spirits would take notice of exemplary filial conduct and reward them with miracles. Tales in which people were unjustly put to death, show Heaven

causing a miracle to indicate their innocence. Local magistrates who ruled with benevolence could also be rewarded with auspicious omens, as well as miraculous protection against locusts, diseases, and bandits. People who were wrongly put to death could appeal to Heaven to gain permission to punish evildoers.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: The spirits of people who die unjustly often administer punishments on the living. In most cases, though, they have to gain Heaven or the Heavenly bureaucracy's permission to do so. Other deities can also punish the living, but their actions can be appealed to Heaven.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Done randomly:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious

group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

Notes: Tian (Heaven) or Tiandi (Heavenly Emperor) ultimately causes a reward to be given, but Heaven might delegate a subordinate to bestow the award.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: With Heaven's permission other supernatural beings can hand out rewards.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

Notes: Tian (Heaven) or Tiandi (Heavenly Emperor) bestows rewards to promote social values, such as filial piety, loyalty, or good governance.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Done randomly:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: One of the most important features of the medieval Confucians is their advocacy of specific virtues. These are ren 仁 (humaneness, compassion, human-heartedness), yi 义 (righteousness, justice, duty), li 礼 (propriety), zhi 智 (wisdom), xin 信 (trustworthiness), xiao 孝 (filial piety), and zhong 忠 (loyalty).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: But only for a limited number of days before one performs a sacrifice.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Notes: If someone didn't perform ancestral sacrifices or engage in the mourning rites for kin, he would have had a hard time being recognized as a Confucian by his peers.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

— I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

— Yes

Notes: How large, official rituals were to be interpreted was often subject to court debate. Confucian scholars would cite different passages from the Confucian Classics to support their interpretation of how the rite should be done.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

— Yes

Notes: Although by no means systematic, if a literatus performed an important ritual incorrectly, he ran the risk of being censured in a memorial to the throne.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

— I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

— Yes

Notes: Yes, sacrificial feasts included the consumption of alcohol. Participants, though, should not drink too much lest they commit improprieties.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

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– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

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Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

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Notes: But only for a limited number of days before one performs a sacrifice.

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Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

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Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

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– No

Specific to this answer:

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– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

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Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

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Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

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Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

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Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

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Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

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Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

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I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

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Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

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– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

Notes: How large, official rituals were to be interpreted was often subject to court debate. Confucian scholars would cite different passages from the Confucian Classics to support their interpretation of how the rite should be done.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Although by no means systematic, if a literatus performed an important ritual incorrectly, he ran the risk of being censured in a memorial to the throne.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

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Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

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– Yes

Notes: Yes, sacrificial feasts included the consumption of alcohol. Participants, though, should not drink too much lest they commit improprieties.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Society and Institutions

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– An empire

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: Education was the means by which one became a Confucian. Two books that were often used as primers during the period were the *Analects* and the *Classic of Filial Piety* -- two of Confucianism's most important texts.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

Notes: Confucianism had no religious professionals.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, when serving as an official of the state, Confucians were sometimes appointed to military offices.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in

question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The state levied taxes on Confucians in their capacity as subjects.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, it was provided by the state, often with the input of Confucian scholars.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an

institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: Since Confucians valued serving others as a vital method of self-cultivation, they often felt the need to become government officials. Even if they chose reclusion rather than officialdom, they often maintained friendly relations with government officials who often happened to be their kinsmen, students, or neighbors.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Famine relief was available through the state. If their family was rich, Confucian scholars could also provide relief to members of their local community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Notes: But since Confucians are supposed to look after the welfare of others, if they were serving as local officials, or if their family had enough wealth, they would often help with water management.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: They were protected by and subject to an institutionalized military provided by the state.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The state would provide water management.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, the state provided an institutionalized judicial system.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: To a small extent, the state might offer poverty relief, or a Confucian who was a local official might also use his office to do so. If individual Confucian scholars had surplus wealth, it was hoped that they would share it with their poorer kin and neighbors. If a Confucian scholar supported a destitute relative or brought him or her into his household, that was also laudatory.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Through the influence of Confucian ideology and office-holders, the state would sometimes provide aid to the elderly and infirm.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The state provided a formal legal code, which was influenced by Confucian considerations.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– An empire

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Famine relief was available through the state. If their family was rich, Confucian scholars could also provide relief to members of their local community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: To a small extent, the state might offer poverty relief, or a Confucian who was a local official might also use his office to do so. If individual Confucian scholars had surplus wealth, it was hoped that they would share it with their poorer kin and neighbors. If a Confucian scholar supported a destitute relative or brought him or her into his household, that was also laudatory.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Through the influence of Confucian ideology and office-holders, the state would sometimes provide aid to the elderly and infirm.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: Education was the means by which one became a Confucian. Two books that were often used as primers during the period were the *Analects* and the *Classic of Filial Piety* -- two of Confucianism's most important texts.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

Notes: Confucianism had no religious professionals.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: Since Confucians valued serving others as a vital method of self-cultivation, they often felt the need to become government officials. Even if they chose reclusion rather than officialdom, they often maintained friendly relations with government officials who often happened to be their kinsmen, students, or neighbors.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Notes: But since Confucians are supposed to look after the welfare of others, if they were serving as local officials, or if their family had enough wealth, they would often help with water management.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The state would provide water management.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The state levied taxes on Confucians in their capacity as subjects.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, the state provided an institutionalized judicial system.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The state provided a formal legal code, which was influenced by Confucian considerations.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, when serving as an official of the state, Confucians were sometimes appointed to military

offices.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: They were protected by and subject to an institutionalized military provided by the state.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, it was provided by the state, often with the input of Confucian scholars.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Wei and Liu Song Dynasties

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